

Keywords:

#MTU, #Quantumcomputing, #TRE, #AWS, #ResearchCollaboration, #IaC, #Sustainability, #EOSCinPractice, #OCRE

QCloud - Ireland's quantum cloud environment

Background

As part of an adoption funding programme supported by the EU and building on experience gained through the GÉANT-led OCRE project, the EOCS Future project allotted a total of €4.8 million across three calls, aimed at bridging the gap between commercial service providers and researchers through the EOCS ecosystem.

The third and last call in the series awarded two projects for making commercial services more accessible to Research & Education communities via the EOCS Marketplace, to digital service aggregators (e.g. non-profit entities, NRENS, RIs and e-Infrastructures, HPC centres, etc.) teaming up with OCRE cloud service providers.

Overview

Harnessing the power of quantum mechanics, this project offers cloud-based access to quantum computing hardware. This breakthrough technology opens avenues for cryptography, networking, data analysis, and optimisation. Researchers gain access to a variety of quantum processors, driving experimentation and innovation. Harnessing quantum computing through the cloud, enables researchers scattered across Ireland to access and leverage this cutting-edge technology, fostering collaboration and accelerating scientific progress.

"Access to quantum computing not only empowers us to personally unveil the advantages of quantum computing in the field of security of autonomous systems and lay the foundation for a quantum-powered future but also enables us to actively engage in software engineering for quantum computing, all while nurturing the minds of the next generation of students and innovators in the realm of quantum knowledge"

Dr Anila Mjeda, CyberSkills, MTU

The Challenge

The Current Entrance Barrier to Quantum Computing Technology

Quantum computing is a disruptive technology that harnesses the laws of quantum mechanics to solve problems outside the scope of our current classical computers. Quantum computers will be a core component of future networks, offering capabilities in cryptography, networking, data analysis and optimization. However, a quantum computer is difficult and expensive to build.

Hazel Murray

PhD and Cybersecurity Lecturer at MTU – Munster Technological University

"The AWS infrastructure and the TRE developed as part of this project will not only improve the quality of Irish quantum research but will also provide ease of collaboration between national and international distributed research teams, promoting cross border collaboration and resource sharing."

Dr Hazel Murray MTU

Quantum computing infrastructure demands exceptionally low temperatures, precise calibration, and expert maintenance, making it a substantial financial and logistical burden for individual researchers or smaller institutions. By providing cloud access, researchers can tap into these cutting-edge quantum resources, democratizing access and fostering innovation in the field of quantum computing. This accessibility not only accelerates scientific discoveries but also fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing among a wider community of researchers, ultimately advancing the frontier of quantum computing research.

This EOCS funding will allow Ireland-based researchers to gain access to public cloud quantum computers through AWS, and support their research. Currently, researchers rely on free introductory credits to run small-scale experiments on the private cloud or on quantum computing simulators. This distribution of cloud access will support greater ambitions within the projects themselves and help familiarise researchers with the commercial services available to support ambitious projects.

The solution & the commercial cloud service

Quantum cloud access for Irish based researchers.

The central platform in which the aggregator, MTU, will promote and stimulate the distribution of Cloud Services within the research community in Ireland, is based on an AWS solution called Trusted Research Environment (TRE). This is a self-service research solution to help secure and analyse data in a collaborative manner, whilst delivering a set of flexible tools and pre-built templates to conduct research at scale. MTU will use the TRE as the centralising mechanism in which it will distribute Quantum Computing capabilities amongst its partners and the wider research community in Ireland.

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The ultimate goal is that any researcher in Ireland with Quantum Computing needs will be able to reach out to MTU and make their case to use the TRE as the platform for their research. This way, MTU aims to facilitate Quantum Computing access to the wider Irish research community.

Based on the advantages of basing quantum computing access on a cloud-based system, MTU will work with researchers across the country to stimulate the distribution of quantum cloud computing. Currently, researchers from 8 Irish universities and 13 research institutes have identified an initial pipeline of nine proposals. The shared goal of these researchers is to combine quantum and classical networking and computing to create the quantum internet and solve the problems of today with the quantum technology of tomorrow.

"Quantum-computer simulations for quantum chemistry can, in principle, yield exact solutions to complex many-body problems. This will enable us to solve materials science problems at a level of accuracy not in reach with standard computers."

Prof. Stefano Sanvito Professor of Condensed Matter Theory, Director of CRANN

IMPACT

Quantum computing is the future of technology

Quantum computing is the technology of the future. It can provide secure communication and data exchange via entangled qubits, it can break our current modern cryptography, it can speed up classical optimization problems allowing faster AI/ML and Data analysis and it can allow us, for the first time, to truly simulate events from the real world that include a degree of randomness. It is a powerful tool which will provide a deeper understanding of the world around us and a strong security system for communications.

Useful material related to this story

MTU

The projects funded by this call will have a direct impact on individuals, businesses and governments who rely on secure communication and transactions; on AI, autonomous vehicles, adaptive living, smart tech and assistive living; on drugs and procedures developed by the pharmaceutical and medical professions and on our understanding of the natural world including predicting the progress and effects of climate change.

As Quantum continues to emerge and increases in importance, it will become essential for students and researchers to have access to quantum computing resources. The scalability of the public cloud ensures that as their field grows in importance and as we move towards a hybrid classical/quantum era, access for all Irish researchers and educators to quantum computing will be feasible. This EOSC funded quantum cloud environment is essential to ensuring the quality and accessibility of this cutting-edge resource, keeping Ireland at the forefront of technological progress, and enabling researchers and developers to test and create quantum algorithms of the future.

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